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Report on co-design of User Profiles and Dashboard Research

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Acronyms

SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

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Publishable Summary

The purpose of the TRIPLE project is to build a web platform (named GoTriple) that will enable the discovery of scientific publications and data in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) domain, and the search for possible collaborators with whom to engage in research projects. In this document we report the results of the activities run in Task 3.4 (Data Driven User Profiles and Dashboards design research) the purpose of which was to design some sections of GoTriple through co-design workshops. The pages to be designed were (1) a private user dashboard (called MyGoTriple) where users will find tailored information strictly related to their activity on the platform, (2) the public user profile that will be their public presentation page on GoTriple, (3) the general dashboard of GoTriple where users will find general information and metrics about the whole platform, and (4) the visual/textual search interface that allows users to browse and filter their search results. We also decided to hold a workshop for a fifth page, the Discipline dashboard, the need for which was not originally envisioned and emerged during the initial user research carried out in Task 3.1.

Dashboards and profiles are common types of pages we find on many different platforms and since these pages can be approached and designed in a variety of ways, we decided to involve real users in the design process by running 5 co-design workshops, involving 18 users among researchers and non-researchers. The workshops were held remotely due to the pandemic and the facilitators had to adapt various brainstorming and co-design methodologies (like Post up, Crazy 8's and voting) to the remote virtual environment, exploiting the features of online services like Miro and Zoom. The remote workshops have proven to be very effective and provided plenty of results and takeaways, some of which confirmed the early assumptions made by the project team and designers, while others introduced new unforeseen ideas and suggestions. Among the many findings that have emerged, there are a few that are worth mentioning here: the public profile pages should allow registered users to show their non-professional and non-academic skills and interests, which can be very useful for involving non-researchers users in research projects where a special knowledge, experience or culture is needed. General information about the TRIPLE project should be provided, to let users know what resources can be found on the platform, and who are the people and institutions that manage the project to prove its reputation and reliability. Keywords can be used as sub-levels of each of the 27 disciplines and could highlight resources with the same keyword patterns that belong to other disciplines, thus allowing to browse the contents crossing disciplines. The size of some fonts and sections of the interface should be increased to make them more readable. The search term is not clearly visible in the search results page.

These and all the other takeaways from the workshop listed in this report will be passed to the design team that will review them and use them in the next design iterations.

1 | INTRODUCTION

This Deliverable 3.4 of the TRIPLE project reports the research activities carried out in Task 3.4 and the results obtained. The scope of the task was to investigate the actual user needs related to various pages and dashboards of the GoTriple platform and more specifically to co-design these pages and dashboards with end-users, via a series of workshops. The pages we planned to research and co-design are: (1) the private user dashboard (called MyGoTriple), (2) the public user profile, (3) the general dashboard for the whole GoTriple platform, (4) the visual/textual search interface. These pages were initially identified in the task description contained in the TRIPLE project proposal. In addition to these pages, we also decided to research and co-design a new and additional page, the Discipline dashboard, where all the data related to each discipline are presented to the user. The need for that additional dashboard emerged clearly from the initial user research which can be consulted in [Deliverable 3.1](#) of the TRIPLE project.

The work for this task consisted in applying a co-design approach, involving actual potential users of the GoTriple platform. A general discussion of the advantages and relevance of the co-design approach for the creation of digital technologies is described in Deliverable 3.2 and the readers are invited to refer to this document for an overview. During the activities for Task 3.4 users were engaged in a series of collaborative online workshops where they were asked to generate ideas, draw sketches and discuss together the various features they expect to find on the platform, in relation to the above mentioned pages and dashboards. The involvement of real users is key to understanding the actual needs of the target audience of a product and allow the team members to go beyond their personal biases.

The outcomes of the research conducted for Task 3.4 are a list of actionable guidelines on how to correct or improve what the consortium has designed so far. All the outcomes of the research conducted for Task 3.4 have been shared with the design team of Net7 and will be shared with the development teams of CNR, CNRS, Know-Center, Net7, Nuromedia, Open Knowledge Maps. It is in fact very important that all the results of the workshops are taken into account in the following phases of the project.

2 | DASHBOARDS AND PROFILE PAGES

Dashboards are a type of user interface that allows a quick overview of a selection of key metrics and information (McArdle and Kitchin, 2016). Digital platforms often have a large amount of data which might be interesting for the users, but it comes in the form of logs or tables: these formats are difficult for users to understand and require an in-depth analysis. Dashboards are a way to select what the most relevant information is and display it in a way that is immediately comprehensible (Smith, 2013). However, it is clear that for dashboards to be of use for the users, they require careful design (Brath and Peter, 2004). Dashboards are thus designed precisely to distill the most relevant information and show it to users with effective interface elements such as indicators, charts and lists of items.

Profile pages are a common type of feature that are available on many platforms: social networks, professional networks, research platforms, sports platforms. Potentially any application that requires user registration can provide a user profile page. This type of page

usually is aimed at presenting the user to the public, displaying the relevant information for the related domain: for example, on LinkedIn the profile page will display all the professional-related information of a person. In this regard profiles may also have some specific functions, depending on the focus/area in which a specific platform operates. In LinkedIn, profiles broadcast skills and experience and thus may be relevant for recruitment (Zide et al. 2014) or for furthering one's career (McCabe, 2017). In research and academic platforms, authors have noted that profiles appear quite pervasive (Martin-Martin et al. 2016) and these can have a variety of purposes such as sharing publications with the community and offering a quicker responsiveness than the traditional publishing does (Ovadia, 2014).

Public profiles of online platforms can normally be associated with processes of self-presentation (e.g. Ellison et al. 2006; Chiang and Suen, 2015), an idea that mirrors what happens offline and which was originally described by the Sociologist Erving Goffman (Miller, 1995; Goffman, 1978). In self-presentation, people select what they would like to show about themselves to other people. In other words, there is a selection process whereby people “put on display” only certain information and not others. Profile pages, for most platforms, can also have their private counterpart, which will be accessible only to the owner, who will access some private information that shouldn't be shared with the public: for example, a sport application (like Strava) provides a private profile where the person can see her/his performance statistics. This aspect also mirrors Goffman theory of self presentation when he spoke about a front-stage and a back-stage. While the front-stage amounts to what people would like to present to others, the back-stage, especially in reference to the digital environments, amount to the space where user can see their information and select which one should be public (front-stage) and which should remain private (Bullingham and Vasconcelos, 2013). In an online platform, profile pages and dashboards can overlap, in particular we can use the dashboard approach to design profile pages where we have a lot of data to show, then using indicators and charts, carefully organized in space paying attention to ordering and hierarchy.

In GoTriple there are five pages for which we planned to adopt the dashboard-approach to optimize the user experience, and to select the relevant information to show. The aim of the **GoTriple dashboard** is to provide an immediate overview of the general metrics of the platform and their evolution in time: users should use this page to get a clue of what the contents and the users of GoTriple are and how these evolved over time. Also the **search interface** can be designed considering it as a sort of dashboard: the results of a search performed by the user on the platform represent a large amount of information that can be approached from a different perspective, visually displayed as charts and indicators. In this case the visual presentation can't replace the normal list view of the search results, but rather complements and enhances it. During the user research ([Deliverable 3.1](#)) we understood that disciplines can function as a compass for moving through the content of the platform. For this reason, we decided to add the **Discipline dashboard**, a page where all the main relevant information about the resources and activities related to a discipline are presented to the user in a visual manner, and where it is possible to access all related resources and profiles. As the name states, this page's user interface will also be approached as a dashboard and for this reason we scheduled a workshop to co-design it with real users.

Finally, the **public user profile** and **private user dashboard** are profile pages (as previously described) for which we would like to adopt some dashboard-like patterns, synthesizing the available data to make them immediately understandable. Profiles emerged clearly as an important user need from [Deliverable 3.1](#), with, in particular, a strong focus on promoting one's work as well as sharing with others the discoveries that are made, and making contacts with other researchers and potential partners.

When designing a dashboard or a profile page the possibilities are endless. It is however of paramount importance to narrow down only some relevant options and for achieving this is fundamental to involve the end-users in this design, in order to identify the design solutions that fully meet the user needs. For this reason, we have planned since the writing stages of the project, to involve potential users of the platform to co-design these pages with them.

3 | WORKSHOPS ORGANIZATION AND METHODOLOGY

Workshops are a very heterogeneous category of activities and can be applied for many different scopes and in different phases of a project. In the context of the TRIPLE project, we decided to use a set of co-design methodologies to generate ideas on what the dashboard and profile pages should look like, to evaluate the assumptions we made during the previous design iterations, to sort generated ideas, and to sketch new user interface concepts. The common factor of all these methodologies is that real users must be involved and that the workshops facilitators' scope is to stimulate discussion and exchange of ideas among all participants, trying to involve them equally.

Co-design research and consequently workshops are organized in divergent and convergent phases (Rowe, 1987): during divergent phases the scope is to obtain the widest possible spread of perspectives and as many and as diverse ideas as the team can produce. The convergent phases are the moment to look at the produced ideas with a critical or realistic eye to narrow them down.

During the workshops we paid special attention not to bias the users and not to give suggestions that could have influenced their creativity. We preferred to leave them a high degree of freedom, even running the risk of getting too generic results.

In total we organised and conducted 5 workshops for Task 3.4, involving 18 researchers from a variety of backgrounds and disciplines. The details of the participants and the mode of organisation of each workshop are provided at the beginning of each section of this deliverable related with said workshops.

3.1 Running remote workshops

The activities of Task 3.4 (Data Driven User Profiles and Dashboards design research) were planned to start in M12 (September 2020): in that period Europe was in the middle of the Covid-19 pandemic so it was not possible to plan face-to-face meetings (in fact all the consortium meeting were held remotely). For this reason, we had to fall back on remote co-design workshops. The whole worldwide community of User Experience (UX) designers and

user researchers was moving to online solutions and so we managed to find a lot of useful resources on how to plan and run an online workshop. An assessment on the available "virtual whiteboard" tools was conducted by Abertay University, and we decided to adopt [Miro](#). The tool proved to be very effective and easy to use, even for workshop participants who were using it for the first time. [Zoom](#) was used as the main communication tool for audio and video chatting for the whole duration of the workshops.

Methodologies like brainstorming, voting and the general online interaction were easy to conduct even in the online virtual environment. The Crazy 8's, which involves sketching on paper by participants (3.5.2), was the method that was more difficult to do without being face-to-face. We can say that despite the unexpected necessity of having to conduct the workshops remotely, we obtained very good results, useful for the purpose of improving the GoTriple project with input from real users.

3.2 Workshops recruitment

The recruitment of participants for the Task 3.4 workshops took place using a variety of channels. The channels we used to recruit participants were:

- the TRIPLE mailing list which we used to invite registered users;
- the GoTriple's website page "[Co-Design Workshops](#)";
- direct contacts among TRIPLE's partners colleagues;
- the "Digital Humanities" public Slack group.

Once the participants for each workshop were found, we shared a Doodle to find the optimal date and time for everyone.

Before the date of each workshop, a detailed agenda was shared to the participants to provide an introduction to the topic of the workshop, to explain which tools were going to be used, to detail the list of the planned activities, and to provide some practical guidelines to optimize the participation. Participants were also asked to sign a consent form providing some information about the participation in the workshop, research data usage and privacy and legal issues. Signed consent forms were then collected by the facilitator.

3.3 Wireframes, interactive prototype and UI mockups

During the first phases of the project, the user experience design team of Net7 had produced visual wireframes of the most important sections of GoTriple: the homepage, the search results, the publication and project pages, and the user profile. Wireframes are a simplified version of each page, designed using grayscale colours and standard fonts: they are useful to start understanding the logical structure of each page, which chunks of information to include, their hierarchy and their relations in space. Wireframes are, by definition, something we keep iterating on, they provide the team a first perspective on a page, to raise usability problems to fix, and to get closer (through iterations) to what will be the final structure. These wireframes

were also used to build an interactive prototype based on the [Invision](#) application. This prototype allows team members and users to navigate a simulated version of the platform moving from one wireframe to another, allowing to get feedback and validate the design decisions taken. Starting from the wireframes, the design team also started defining the look and feel of the GoTriple platform, laying down the first mockups of what will be the final user interface (UI); the design of the interface was done taking into account the work previously done in work package 8 (WP8) and described in the deliverable [D8.2 Communication Toolkit](#).

The wireframes, the interactive prototype and the user interface mockups were used during some of the workshops to submit the design work done to the participants and elicit their feedback and impressions, or to show a first overview of the platform and provide some context.

3.4 Workshops introductions

Each workshop started with an introductory part useful to get to know the participants, to allow them to get familiar with Miro and to introduce them to the TRIPLE project.

The presentation board was used as an ice-breaker activity, to share some professional and personal information and to allow the participants to familiarize with the notes in Miro, which are later used in all the activities. Figure 1 shows this initial stage of the workshop through the Miro white board.

NAME	Frank	Clara	Sauro	Marta	Helen	NAME
WHERE ARE YOU?	Pisa, Italy	Lucern	Prague	Barcelona, Spain	Berlin	WHERE ARE YOU?
WHERE DO YOU WORK?	Net7 in Pisa	I am Head of Digital Humanities	Prague University	University of Barcelona	Small company	WHERE DO YOU WORK?
WHAT IS YOUR PROFESSION?	User Experience designer	Academic researcher and manager	Project manager	Researcher on ancient economy and science manager	Developer	WHAT IS YOUR PROFESSION?
WHAT ARE YOUR HOBBIES?	Surfing, traveling	Yoga	Hiking, reading, cycling	Climbing, staying in nature	Play football, read	WHAT ARE YOUR HOBBIES?

FIGURE 1 - THE PRESENTATIONS BOARD IN MIRO (NAMES ARE FICTITIOUS).

After the initial introduction and familiarisation, we moved to a board where the GoTriple platform was briefly presented to provide some context to the group (Figure 2).

FIGURE 2 - THE GOTRIPLE PRESENTATION BOARD.

During some workshops, the participants were also introduced to some pages of the interactive prototype of the interface, to provide a more accurate context.

3.5 Methodologies

This section briefly describes the main methodologies and techniques that were used during the workshops, in order to co-design with end-users the profiles and the dashboards.

3.5.1 Post up

One of the techniques we used for our workshops was the Post up. Post up is a divergent methodology that is used to help participants produce as many ideas as possible on a topic (Gray, D. et al., 2010, Straker, D., 1997). This type of activity is used to fuel creativity avoiding critical thinking and skepticism, embracing brainstorming and optimism. Starting from an overarching question, participants are asked to write their ideas on notes: this activity is timeboxed, usually for 10 minutes.

At the end of the 10 minutes, each participant is asked to present her/his notes to the whole group. This is a very important part of the activity because it is where we better understand the perspective of all the participants, where they can discuss ideas among them, and also more shy ones can express their ideas and be listened to.

During notes presentation, the workshop's facilitator will overlap similar notes one to the other, to highlight recurring ideas and patterns. This clustering is also useful for the following voting session.

The overarching question must be concise, clear and unambiguous. Before starting the actual Post up, the facilitator asks the participants if the question is clear, and, if there is any doubt, tries to explain it better to dispel any ambiguity.

3.5.2 Crazy 8's

[Crazy 8's](#) is an activity of the Google Design Sprint in which we challenge participants to sketch eight ideas in eight minutes. This is also a divergent methodology and it is useful to foster creativity: usually the first two or three sketches come easy while it becomes harder and harder

to sketch the remaining ones. The process of pushing the participants creativity to the limit, asking them to sketch more ideas is aimed at producing unexpected and unobvious results (that's what we're looking for).

It is important that participants do not feel pressure to produce high quality sketches, for this reason the workshop's facilitator normally provides them with markers with a medium tip and with some examples that show the low quality we expect: we are looking for ideas not for high quality drawings.

The produced sketches should be presented and discussed together, to share the perspective of each person in the group.

This methodology was adopted during the workshop on the Discipline dashboard and even if it was fruitful, it probably had some limits when conducted remotely. The problems that we noticed are that it was impossible to provide the participants with the right markers and paper sheets, and that we couldn't encourage participants to produce more sketches, with the result that some produced fewer than expected.

3.5.3 Voting

After the participants have generated some ideas during divergent activities, they were then allowed some time to converge these to a refined list of results.

FIGURE 3 - EXAMPLE OF NOTES AFTER A POST UP ACTIVITY CONDUCTED FOR TASK 3.4.

As displayed in Figure 3, the result of a brainstorming session can normally be a chaotic list of notes, some of which are clustered during the presentation. It is very difficult to gain some practical outcomes out of this disordered list of elements. To start narrowing down the ideas

and converge toward some of the most promising, a useful technique is to ask participants to vote on the various ideas, to prioritize them and agree on what is more relevant. When using Miro, it's necessary to clean up this board before voting, since Miro allows voting on a single note, and clusters (which are composed of many notes) would be difficult to vote on. That's why each cluster must be transformed into a single note that summarizes the idea, as shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4 - THE IDEAS GENERATED DURING THE POST UP AFTER THE CLEAN UP (READY FOR THE VOTING SESSION) FROM ONE OF THE TASK 3.4 WORKSHOPS.

Participants will have a number of votes available, which is generally calculated as the total number of notes divided by 3. It is good practice to provide a few minutes to allow participants to vote and then to review the results together, asking for the participants' feedback. The result of a voting session on Miro is depicted in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5 - PRIORITIZED IDEAS AFTER THE VOTING FROM ONE OF THE TASK 3.4 WORKSHOPS.

It is important to note that the designers of a project will not rely solely on the results of the voting, but they must also take into account the other ideas and everything that is said during the workshop.

3.5.4 Affinity mapping

We adopted affinity mapping to perform a deep analysis of everything that emerged during the workshops. Even if we have the voting results as a final outcome of the workshop, we want to be sure that we don't miss a bit of anything relevant that was said during the activity: participants usually don't write everything on notes, but they give interesting insights as they talk, that's what we are looking for with affinity mapping. This methodology is applied after the workshop has ended, usually not more than a few days later. The video recording of the workshop was reviewed and each interesting idea or remark by the participants was written on a paper note and attached on a physical white board. Then the similar notes are overlapped and clustered as we did virtually during the Post up (Takashi Iba et al. 2017): these clusters represent the main ideas that emerged during the conversation with the participants. Most of these will correspond (and confirm) what already stated in the previous activities, some others will add some useful information that otherwise would be lost.

It will then be up to the designer to understand the importance and priority of these ideas and how to apply them to the design of the project.

4 | INSIGHTS

In this section we will review in detail the outcomes of the workshops. For each workshop we highlight the key takeaways, which represent the most important ideas and suggestions that arose from the activities and conversation with the participants. The key takeaways are usually strictly related to the section of the platform the workshop is focused on. Ideas that were not related to the main focus of the workshop are listed in the Other outcomes sections, where it is possible to find general suggestions for the GoTriple platform or for other pages.

Since it's imperative that all these takeaways don't get lost in the process, we distilled them in sections called "How to improve the GoTriple design" (section 4 in each workshop), where we summarized the main outcomes that the user experience designers must take into account when working on the wireframes of the interface.

Not all the ideas and suggestions emerged during the workshops will make their way into the platform: designers have a key role here to check the priorities, to understand what it make sense to add to the project and what is outside of its main scope, and to discuss with the development team to understand what is feasible and what is not.

The workshops are reported in chronological order.

4.1 The public user dashboard: Profile page

This is the first workshop of Task 3.4. It was held in March 2021 with 5 participants. Originally planned for 2 hours, the workshop lasted about 3 hours: this first experience was useful to better plan the agenda of the following workshops. The participants were guided through two Post up sessions and a voting activity to converge on the most relevant ideas.

4.1.1 Workshop information

Number of participants: 5

Duration: 3 hours

Day: 24th March 2021

Methodologies: Post up (x2), Voting, Affinity mapping (for reviewing).

Facilitator: Giulio Andreini - Net7

4.1.2 Key takeaways

This section presents the most important takeaways we got from this workshop. Some of them were highlighted as a result of the voting session: these are the features of the Profile page on the importance of which participants agreed during the workshop. Some other key aspects emerged during the affinity mapping analysis.

Voting session:

- Collaboration status (4 votes):** the fact that a user is open to collaboration or seeking collaborators is something very important that we should highlight in the Profile page.
- Projects (4 votes):** the Profile Page should display the present and past projects a user was involved in (like LinkedIn). Also, non-researchers should be included in projects (in order to attest to their participation and reward them). Projects will be a way to navigate the network of collaborators.
- Co-workers and collaborators (3 votes):** the public user profile dashboard should show links to people who co-authored publications with the profile owner. This will allow another user, once landed on the Profile page, to continue browsing by visiting the pages of collaborators, who might be interesting people to get in contact with or to start a project with.
- Past and current institutional and professional affiliations (2 votes):** displaying the previous affiliations on a researcher's profile will allow users to understand her/his experience and knowledge, and to understand if they have some shared contacts that could be exploited to get some references or to get in touch.
- Skills, know-how, interests (2 votes):** know-how and personal interests not related to the academic experience of a person are very important, especially for non-researcher users (like citizens, entrepreneurs or policy makers).
- Resources by the user (2 votes):** all the publications of the user should be listed in her/his Profile page, and open access resources should be highlighted. This will be useful to find reusable data.
- Disciplines and keywords description (2 votes):** each profile should be described by disciplines of interest or keywords.
- Relations with other platform profiles (2 votes):** direct links to profile pages on other platforms should be provided (ORCID, ResearchGate, Academia, LinkedIn). Universal identifiers (like ORCID) should be displayed on the page, when available.
- Messaging (2 votes):** since one of the main scopes of the Profile page is to connect with potential collaborators, we should provide a way for users to get in touch (like a messaging or chat system).

Additional takeaways:

- Affiliation to non-institutional groups and networks:** persons with a special interest or skill usually belong or participate in non-institutional groups (like meetups), thus these affiliations can be a relevant information to show on the user profile, because it indicates the deep knowledge of a certain topic.
- Current focus and future plans:** apart from the current project a person is working on, it can be of some interest to know which will be her/his future plans, fields of interests or research focus. This information can be useful to understand whether to get in touch with a person for future collaborations.
- Spoken languages:** this is a very important information for two main reasons: (1) to know if two users speak a common language (and if they will be able to communicate easily) and

Related to the Profile page:

- Even if researchers might have more than one profile on different platforms (ResearchGate, Academia, LinkedIn) some could decide to rely solely on GoTriple to display all their professional information.
- It must be possible to import data from other platforms (like ORCID) to avoid double inserting the same information.
- The Profile page should show statistics of the resources of the user on charts on an annual basis.
- Sense of cultural identity of the user: nationality or culture. It is important for users to display where they belong to. This could be useful when searching for collaborators (e.g. you're making a study on Bask culture and you are looking for collaborators that belong to the Bask Country and identify with the Bask culture).
- Not all platforms like GoTriple, ORCID, RG, Academia, LinkedIn should show the same full set of data of the user: some users could decide to show different sets of data on the various platforms.

Related to GoTriple in general (not strictly related to the Profile page):

- Users shouldn't receive spam or continuously bump into paywalls (as it happens with ResearchGate and Academia).
- It is very important for researchers to be able to access the full text and full data of publications; freely accessible resources should be highlighted and easily findable.
- The download of papers should be done from the websites of the repositories where the resources are originally stored, so that these can track users' traffic and download metrics. Direct PDF download from GoTriple should be avoided: from GoTriple, users should land on the repository website, and download the resource from there.
- Personalised notifications for the user: the platform should include a recommender system that alerts the user when some resources related to her/his interests, to the followed users or to the followed disciplines are added to GoTriple.

4.1.4 How to improve the GoTriple design

Designers and team members always develop a biased vision of a product: this workshop allowed us to see the Profile page from a different perspective, with the eyes of the actual users of the platform.

During the session, there was an unexpected focus on users' expertise that lies outside of their school or academic career, but within the sphere of personal knowledge and skill. This is something we hadn't planned before but actually can be of great interest in developing projects involving non-researchers or researchers with special interests.

Another key aspect is that the Profile page must be functional to find collaborators and therefore all the reported information must be aimed at this purpose.

As a result, in addition to the sections and contents already planned, this workshop suggested that we should add information like the collaboration status, the coworkers and collaborators

network, the spoken language, the location of the person and all the information about the personal skills and non-institutional groups affiliations.

4.2 The general GoTriple dashboard

The GoTriple dashboard will be a page that is related to the whole platform: its scope is to provide an overview of the contents and metrics of GoTriple, and to display "what is happening" of the platform. One could think of many alternative ways on how to design this page, that's why we planned a workshop to involve users in the design process, in order to reduce the possible options and take some key decisions. This was probably the most difficult workshop we held, due to the fact that the GoTriple dashboard is so generic and abstract that it wasn't easy for participants to produce ideas strictly related to this page. In fact, some outcomes are related to the platform in general, while others are related to tailored contents for registered users: in these cases the outcomes are not specifically related to the GoTriple dashboard (however, they are still useful for platform design).

4.2.1 Workshop information

Number of participants: 4

Duration: 2:30 hours

Day: 8th June 2021

Methodologies: Post up, Voting, Affinity mapping (for reviewing)

Facilitator: Giulio Andreini - Net7

4.2.2 Key takeaways

These are the most relevant takeaways that emerged during the Post up and voting activities of the workshop (Figure 7 and Figure 8).

- How-to and help (3 votes):** contextual help and how-to section with detailed tutorials on how to use the platform, should be part of this dashboard. The dashboard page could present a clear link to the How-to section.
- What's new/Platform updates (2 votes):** the dashboard should include updates on the development of the platform like new features released, new providers or new resources added.
- What's inside GoTriple (1 vote):** the dashboard should provide information about where its data (publications and data sets) is collected from and, therefore, what can be found on the platform. This is an important point to allow users to understand if GoTriple is the right service to do a certain task. Users complain that sometimes they try to do a certain job on a platform that is not the right one (where lately they discover they won't find what they need) thus wasting a lot of time.
- Trust and reputation (1 vote):** who is managing and runs the platform. We need to build credibility and reputation so that users can trust GoTriple.

- **User types chart (1 vote):** the dashboard could include a visual chart depicting the types of users registered on GoTriple. Additionally, we could show the evolution of users over time.
- **Most searched terms chart (1 vote):** the dashboard could include a chart or list that shows what are the most searched terms on the platform. Google Trends could be an inspiration for this.
- **Disciplines with chart (1 vote):** the dashboard could include a graph showing the disciplines most featured on the platform. A yearly trend chart could also be used.

FIGURE 7 - THE IDEA WALL WHERE THE NOTES WERE ORGANIZED AND CLUSTERED DURING THE PRESENTATION OF THE POST UP SESSION. THIS ACTIVITY LED TO THE MAIN KEY TAKEAWAYS OF THE WORKSHOP.

FIGURE 8 - THE RESULTS OF THE VOTE: THE VOTE PROVIDED SOME PRIORITISATION OF THE NOTES GENERATED DURING THE POST UP ACTIVITY. CARDS NOT STRICTLY RELATED TO THE GOTRIPLE DASHBOARD WERE NOT TAKEN INTO ACCOUNT FOR THE DESIGN OF THE PAGE.

4.2.3 Other outcomes

These are other outcomes that are not strictly related to the GoTriple dashboard, but that are more relevant to the platform in general. Even if these will not impact the design of the dashboard, we will take them into account as general guidelines. Some of these confirm what emerged from the interviews ([Deliverable 3.1](#)) and the other workshops. Most of these outcomes emerged during the affinity mapping analysis (3.5.4) done when reviewing the recording of the workshop. Figure 9 shows the physical whiteboard during the analysis.

- Platform reliability and long-term durability:** choosing to work on a platform is a sort of investment for users. If they start working on GoTriple, registering and adding a lot of data (like collections, saved searches, followed users) and after a couple of years the platform is closed, they have wasted a lot of time and energy. Users would like to know that the platform is a long-term project and that they are not wasting their time.
- Types of resources:** the different types of resources available on GoTriple (e.g. articles, blog posts, presentations) should be visually well distinguished; users should be able to filter search results based on their type.
- Free resources:** it is important for the users to be able to clearly distinguish open access/freely available resources from those that can't be downloaded in full text, and to filter them in search results and lists.

- **General UX suggestions:** the user interface must allow many hours of working without tiring the user (like ResearchGate does). The user experience must be easy for the novice users, but allow advanced and complex interaction for the experts.
- **Personalized content:** the data and news from people, projects, and disciplines that the user is following seem more suitable for the MyGoTriple page (4.3).
- **Recommendations:** publications and datasets recommended for the logged user do not appear strictly related to the dashboard. Recommendations appear more suitable for the MyGoTriple page (4.3).
- **GoTriple as the main platform:** GoTriple should offer all the features users need for discovery and to find potential collaborators, and should provide access to the widest availability of resources; in this way it could become researchers' main working tool and avoid them having to use multiple platforms for the same purposes.
- **Tags added by users:** users should have the possibility to tag resources, especially in their collections (also adding new tags).
- **Shared collections:** collections should be shared among registered users to empower collaboration.
- **Community:** there's a recurring concept of community that somehow resembles that of a social network. The basic features for the community should be the possibility to follow other registered users (and get notified when some new resources related to them are added on GoTriple) and to get in touch with them using a messaging system.
- **Job board:** a job listings section where SMEs and NGOs can do some recruitment, could be a useful addition to the platform.
- **Social share:** the possibility to share resources on social networks may also be a useful feature to add.

FIGURE 9 - THE PHYSICAL WHITEBOARD WHERE THE AFFINITY MAPPING ANALYSIS WAS DONE: THIS ACTIVITY ALLOWED US TO FIND SOME INTERESTING IDEAS THAT EMERGED DURING THE CONVERSATION WITH THE PARTICIPANTS.

4.2.4 How to improve the GoTriple design

In the design of the platform we should add in-context help (like tooltips and brief texts) and a help section with how-to's and tutorials.

It will be also important to provide some general information about the project: what resources can be found inside GoTriple, who runs the project (the team and institutions behind it) to prove its reputation and reliability.

Participants also underlined they would like to know about the platform updates, especially new features released and new resources added.

All this information doesn't necessarily need to go in the GoTriple dashboard (where it could be simply linked) but rather belong to the informative and help sections of the platform.

Instead, the suggested charts (user types, most searched terms, disciplines) will be an important part of the dashboard, providing some immediate visual feedback on the contents and the activity on GoTriple.

4.3 The private user dashboard: MyGoTriple

This session was run with 4 participants in July 2020 to gain feedback on the interface design for the MyGoTriple area of the platform. Participants were shown a selection of different competitors' screenshots for personalised landing pages (Google Scholar, Academia and ResearchGate) and were asked about their preferences for these designs. They were then guided through each of the MyGoTriple interfaces previously prepared by the Net7's design team (copied over to a Miro board) and asked about their opinions on the functionality, design, and navigation flow of the platform. Participants were also presented with 3 alternative options for the overall look and feel of the platform and asked which of these they preferred.

4.3.1 Workshop information

Number of participants: 4

Duration: One Hour

Day: 7th July 2021

Methodologies: Feedback on Design Wireframes/overall platform design

Facilitator: Paula Forbes - Abertay University

4.3.2 Key takeaways

The following are the key takeaways from this workshop:

- Competitor benchmarking:** of the 3 competitor pages, the participants much preferred the design of Academia.edu. They commented that they didn't really like the visual design of ResearchGate and that Google Scholar was too simplistic.
- Publication date:** recommended articles often lack the publication date that is important to the article's relevance.
- Look and feel:** overall the participants liked the look and feel of the MyGoTriple platform interfaces they were presented with.
- "Pundit" label:** naming of "Pundit" notifications was unclear - as people don't know that Pundit is the annotation service.
- New registered users' metric:** not sure that people will be interested in the number of new registered users which is shown.
- Personalised messages:** personalised messages could be larger, and given more priority than the generalised GoTriple Updates in the "What's New" section.
- Font size:** characters are too small compared to the numbers in the above notifications (icons would be really useful here too).

- Improve messages section legibility:** in "Messages", the size of the message box could be increased and the left hand side list of messages decreased to improve legibility of the message to be read.
- Archived messages grouping:** some participants asked for the possibility to group messages when they are archived.
- Attached files:** the platform should provide the possibility to attach a file when sending a message.
- "Collections" label:** participants were unsure about the use of the "Collections" tab - is this for saved items? Perhaps a bookmark icon/label would be better.
- Improve recommendations section legibility:** in the "Recommendations" section the left hand menu is taking up too much space, could increase the "Publications" box on the right to make this section more legible.
- Options after "Select All":** it's not clear to participants what options become available if they click on "Select All" within the recommended Publications.
- "Saved Searches":** "Saved Searches" was liked a lot. We may need to add page numbers once there are more than a handful of these.
- Icons for Publications, Projects, People:** icons would be useful for the three different options (Publications, Projects, People).
- Disciplines and colour:** participants liked the Disciplines boxes and the associated icons a lot, but disliked the Khaki green colour.

4.3.3 Other outcomes

In addition to the above comments, one participant asked if the purple colour for the platform had anything to do with the feminist movement. Orange was liked as an "Action" colour for clickable links (eg. the Search button and the Sign-Up button).

4.3.4 How to improve the GoTriple design

- Increase the size of the characters for each item presented in the "What's New" section.
- Include icons for the various different items in the "What's New" section and elsewhere, (e.g. messages, recommendations, resources, publications, datasets, projects).
- Adjust the size of personalised messages, to give priority over the generalised GoTriple Updates below.
- Ensure the "Sign Up to GoTriple" message is clear, perhaps include a web version alongside the mobile image.

4.4 The Discipline dashboard

As anticipated earlier in the deliverable, the Discipline dashboards were not initially envisioned in the platform architecture. During the user research conducted for T3.1 and reported in the [Deliverable 3.1](#), we understood that it would have been necessary to give centrality to the disciplines; in fact, each discipline can be seen as a compass, useful to discover all its related resources (like publications, data sets and project), and to find profiles of users who work or

who are interested in fields related to that discipline. For this reason in GoTriple there will be 27 Discipline dashboards, one for each of the disciplines identified by the EU-financed project [Mapping of research in european social sciences and humanities](#) (MORESS).

In order to get some ideas on how to structure these dashboards, we decided to conduct a co-design workshop. This activity made us discover some interesting and unexpected results related to these pages and to GoTriple in general. In the first part of the workshop we provided some general information about the logical structure of the contents of GoTriple to allow participants to understand how disciplines are related to the resources and the user' profiles (Figure 10).

FIGURE 10 - THE DIAGRAM THAT WAS USED TO EXPLAIN THE PARTICIPANTS THE RELATIONS EACH DISCIPLINE HAS WITH THE OTHER RESOURCES AND ENTITIES OF GOTRIPLE.

Then we provided a brief overview of some possible interface solutions to display contents and relations (Figure 11). We tried not to bias the participants, but this step was necessary since they were asked to design some sketches.

FIGURE 11 - EXAMPLES OF HOW DATA CAN BE DISPLAYED USING DIFFERENT VISUALIZATIONS.

This workshop was particularly fruitful and allowed us to consider solutions that we wouldn't have thought of otherwise.

4.4.1 Workshop information

Number of participants: 3

Duration: 2:20 hours

Date: 13th July 2021

Methodologies: Post up, Crazy 8's, Voting, Affinity mapping (for reviewing)

Facilitator: Giulio Andreini - Net7

4.4.2 Key takeaways

The workshop included a Post up activity (Figure 12) and then a sketching phase using the Crazy 8's method (Figure 13). As expected, most of the outcomes from the ideation session were included by the participants also in their sketches. Participants were asked to vote directly on the sketches that were produced (and not on the ideas as was the case with the other workshops). In this section we report the main takeaways that emerged during voting of the

sketches and a few more that were highlighted by the affinity mapping review of the workshop's recording.

FIGURE 12 - THE IDEAS GENERATED BY THE PARTICIPANTS DURING THE POST UP ACTIVITY OF THE WORKSHOP (NAMES ARE FICTITIOUS).

FIGURE 13 - THE SKETCHES PRODUCED BY THE PARTICIPANTS DURING THE CRAZY 8'S ACTIVITY (NAMES ARE FICTITIOUS).

FIGURE 14 - DETAILS OF SKETCHES DONE BY THE PARTICIPANTS.

Voting session:

- Interdisciplinarity by keywords (2 votes):** the goal of interdisciplinary is to connect and integrate several disciplines, and avoid that researchers work in isolated domains, without connecting with other contexts and researchers. Since keywords are shared by resources among disciplines, they could be used to fuel interdisciplinarity: in each Discipline dashboard we could show the resources that share the same keywords and that also belong to other disciplines. So, as an example, in the Psychology page, it may be possible to show resources that belong also to Education (which share the same keywords e.g. learning processes).
- Disciplines network chart (2 votes):** a chart or visualizations that shows:
 - the relation of the current discipline with the other disciplines (or)
 - the relation of the current discipline with the related keywords (and thus with other disciplines) (or)
 - the relation of the user with the current discipline and related keywords.

The chart could be interactive allowing users to navigate it, in order to increase their capacity to discover new things.
- Discipline page search bar (2 votes):** search input that allows to perform a search within the current discipline.
- Keywords bar chart (2 votes):** a bar chart with the most common keywords within a discipline.

- What's new in the discipline (2 votes):** the discipline page should provide information on the new related contents, like new publications, new datasets, new findings in the field. This information could be presented as a data-sorted list or as a timeline. This section would be useful to engage users in coming back to this page, thus improving the retention of the whole GoTriple platform.
- News and events (2 votes):** the Discipline dashboard could also display some contents like news, events, workshops, meetings, awards, and any other time-based information that might be useful for users interested in the discipline. These news could be generated in these ways:
 - added by the community members; there is a team of people providing information (or)
 - provided by an external service, that given a discipline, returns this type of information (or)
 - the feed is automatically built within GoTriple with all the information retrieved from the users that belong to the discipline (in this case there will not be "external" data like workshops and events).
- Disciplines icons (1 vote):** disciplines should be described visually using illustrations or icons, to make them more recognizable and easily understood.

Additional takeaways:

- Most active publishing companies and institutions chart:** publishing companies and institutions are fundamental information, so they could be displayed in each Discipline page using a list or a chart showing those that are more active in that domain.
- Recommendations within the discipline:** in the discipline page it could be relevant to provide some recommendations for the user (publications, projects, people) filtered by the current discipline.
- Types of resources chart:** bar chart that displays the types of resources within a discipline.

4.4.3 Other outcomes

This section lists the takeaways that are not strictly related to the Discipline dashboard, but rather related to other pages of the platform or to GoTriple in general:

- Keywords as sub-disciplines:** all the participants stressed out the importance of sub-disciplines, meaning whatever can act as a logical sub-level division of a discipline: sub-disciplines should be used to describe and refine the resources of each discipline. Since in GoTriple there will not be "official" sub-disciplines, we could rely on keywords that are less hierarchical but more versatile.
- Discipline's community:** participants introduced the concept of community of active users in a discipline. This ranges from a "light-community" where users who have published the most recent resources in the discipline are highlighted in a page, to a "real-community" paradigm, where selected and active users in the discipline somehow control the contents of the page (and might even run a forum or similar community app).

- ❑ **Discipline following:** it could be relevant to design a system that allows registered users to follow a certain discipline and get notified when some new related resources are added to GoTriple or when a new person working on that discipline has registered.
- ❑ **Filter by publishing companies and institutions:** users should be able to filter the list of search results by the publishing company or institution.
- ❑ **Filter by keywords:** keywords should be also used to filter the resources (in the search results page).
- ❑ **Resources discipline improved by users:** when a user claims a publication or project she/he has the possibility of reviewing and improving the discipline information.

FIGURE 15 - THE PHYSICAL WHITEBOARD WHERE THE AFFINITY MAPPING ANALYSIS WAS DONE. MOST OF THE "OTHER OUTCOMES" WERE HIGHLIGHTED DURING THE AFFINITY MAPPING.

4.4.4 How to improve the GoTriple design

The design of the Discipline dashboard should take into account the outcomes of the related workshop. The most common keywords of a discipline (those that are most often linked to the resources) should be visible to users as they represent the logical sub-level of each discipline: these keywords could be represented as a list or as a chart. Moreover, keywords can be exploited to filter the resources within a discipline. Each Discipline dashboard could also display sections with resources from other disciplines that share the same keywords: this would facilitate navigation across domains and interdisciplinary research.

The dashboard should include a search bar to search within the current discipline, a bar chart depicting the types of resources and a chart with the publishing companies and institutions that

are the most active in that domain. Workshop participants requested the option of following each discipline, and getting notifications when a new corresponding resource is added or a new user working in that discipline has registered on GoTriple.

Each Discipline dashboard should be constantly updated, displaying related newly added resources and newly registered users; participants also requested the possibility to have news and information about events, conferences, workshops, meetings and awards that are relevant for users interested in each discipline. This would shape the Discipline dashboard into an omni-comprehensive page that users interested in a field could refer to, to see what's new and stay up to date. Even if this goes beyond the scope of the TRIPLE project, it is an interesting idea for possible future developments.

4.5 Search Results page (list and dashboard view)

This work focuses on the results of any search made by users on the GoTriple platform. Two separate individual Miro workshop sessions were run to get feedback on the design of the Search Results pages. Being able to focus on an individual's comments was useful though and allowed for rich and in-depth focus on the design and on following up any interesting comments made by the individual that is not always possible in a group setting.

4.5.1 Workshop information

Number of participants: 2 individual one-to-one sessions

Duration: one hour each

Day(s): Wednesday 14th July and Thursday 29th July 2021

Methodologies: Walkthrough of Interface Design Wireframes to obtain feedback

Facilitator: Paula Forbes - Abertay University

4.5.2 Key takeaways

Initial Search Screen:

- Advanced Search button visibility:** the "Advanced Search" option is a bit small, it is present but not that obvious that it is clickable (participants suggested that many researchers will use this option a lot).
- Percentage of Open Access articles:** participants commented positively on the fact that users can see how many articles are available in Open Access.

Search Results Screen:

- Publications, Projects, Profiles tabs:** the Publications, Projects, Profiles tab headings could be larger and icons would be helpful in order to easily tell them apart.

- Search term visibility:** the Search term used is not visible. Perhaps the search was made by selecting the disciplines shown on the left, but the user would expect to see the search terms used.
- Authors' affiliation:** it would be nice to see the affiliation of the authors for the publications presented.
- Results sorting:** for participants it was not clear if the Default order is the most recent or most relevant. Participants remarked that the most relevant is not always the most trusted.
- Results sorting by author:** participants also suggested that a "Sort by author" option could be a useful addition for the search.
- "Knowledge Map" and "Streamgraph" meaning:** from the current design it is not immediately clear what the "Knowledge Map" and "Streamgraph" tabs are (i.e. there are no icons on the wireframe used).
- Articles' titles:** participants suggested that the titles of the articles could be a little bigger.
- Unclear keywords in article previews:** participants also remarked that it is unclear what is meant by the "Academic terms" in article subheading - does it mean Keywords?
- "Save Search" or "Search History":** there were also comments on whether the users will use the "Save Search" option, it might be more useful to just be able to see your "Search History" with the option to view the last search session (or last 10 searches).

List/Visual tabs:

- "Visual" tab:** the "List" option is expected, and the meaning is clear, but participants were not sure what would be seen in the "Visual" tab. Users would not know what to expect from this label.
- "Visual" tab:** participants suggested that the "Visual" tab could be moved over to the right next to "Knowledge Map" and "Streamgraph" to make it more obvious that it is something different to explore, it might be better labelled "Graphical" or "Visual overview" (and include an icon to help with the lack of understanding mentioned above).
- Charts colours:** colours used in the Visual charts are a bit light, they could be stronger to give better contrast (useful in more difficult lighting situations and on mobile devices).

FIGURE 16 - SCREENSHOT OF MIRO WORKSHOP SHOWING PARTICIPANT COMMENTS ON THE VISUAL SEARCH INTERFACE.

FIGURE 17 - INTERFACE MOCKUP OF GOTRIPLE SEARCH INTERFACE - SHOWING RESULTS OF A SEARCH.

Language:

- Language filter:** participants commented that from the interface, it is not clear how the "Language" options work, which suggests the interface needs to be clearer on this aspect.
- Language and search results:** the option to download articles in different languages may be surprising to users: participants expressed the expectation that they will be given results in English, if English is used in search terms, or in French, if French terms are used. This would need to be explained if this is not the case.
- Default language:** it emerged that it is not really clear what is the default language and it may be better to ask the user what they want in terms of language search (what is the default?).
- Language option functionality:** participants also stated that it is not quite clear if the language option shows publications available in the language selected, or if it allows seeing a translation of a publication into that language. Likely to be what's available, but it should be explained.

Selected publication page:

- Full article availability on GoTriple:** there were aspects which were not immediately clear from the interface in relation to the page showing the selected publication. For example it was not clear whether the full article can be read directly from the platform without downloading or just the abstract or if they can read it by the "Go to Page" option (top right).
- Origin site:** participants also remarked that viewing the site of origin may help with assessing the trustworthiness of the article.
- "Similar articles" tab suggestion:** participants suggested that it would be nice to see how this article relates to other articles, perhaps by showing a list of other related ones, "Similar articles" - could be a fourth tab after "Recommended", "Related Projects", and "From the same authors".
- Metrics:** for the graphs on the right (Shares, Views, Downloads) not sure if "Shares" is important, there are more important metrics such as citations which would be better.

Search Profiles:

- Profiles to discover researchers:** participants generally commented positively on how the profiles are presented. One participant recalled that she recently wanted to find someone for an Erasmus project and would have found the search profile useful. This suggests that this feature can increase the discoverability of researchers.
- "Open to Collaboration" functionality:** the "Open to Collaboration" status was commented as a positive aspect of the profile which can likely help with fostering novel collaborations. However, one participant was not clear on what happens with the "Open to collaboration" tab. Is it clickable? Does it open a pre-filled Contact form?
- "Open to collaboration" filter:** on this same aspect, participants commented that it would be nice to have the option to only view or filter out researchers who are "Open to collaboration".
- "Not interested/I'm too busy" status:** they also commented that perhaps another status could be "Not interested/I'm too busy".

FIGURE 18 - SCREENSHOT FROM THE SEARCH WORKSHOP SHOWING COMMENTS ON SEARCHING PEOPLE INTERFACE.

- "Search in name and metadata" not clear:** one participant remarked that in the filter options, the statement "Search in name and metadata" is not clear.
- Skills and know-how difference:** likewise, the difference between skills and know-how was commented as not being entirely clear and perhaps skills/interests should be in separate search areas.
- "Nationality":** for "Nationality", it might be better to have "Country working in" instead as it could possibly create cultural bias.

Search Projects:

- Current search term:** in the "Your Search" area, there is a box with the text "Impressionism" and a "x" next to it, is this the search term used? What Search term was used isn't that clear - it should be more visible.
- Date chart:** publication date graph with an option to adjust the results was commented on as being a useful feature.
- Participating countries and disciplines:** an option to view the "Countries Participating" in a project would be good together with the different disciplines involved.
- Project logo:** it would be nice to display the project logo or icon next to the title (when available).
- Institutions involved:** where the co-ordinator of the project is shown, it would be good to see the other institutions involved (but appreciate that the list may be long and space is

limited - maybe possibly viewed when project is clicked). Need to see connections to other countries and institutions.

- **People who viewed the project metric:** mixed feedback on seeing the number of people who've viewed the project (eye icon): one participant said it was useful, the other said it was not so important. By the way, this could be very important to the people involved in the project.
- **Projects sorting:** participants were not sure that "Most recent" makes sense for projects since projects have a start and end date; probably it would be better to have "Most recently started", "Most recently finished" and "Most recently published". They also commented that it would be good to see which projects are still active.
- **Additional filters:** options to filter by "Funder", "Type of grant" and "Coordinator" are probably helpful.

4.5.3 Other outcomes

Overall colour scheme and design:

- **User interface alternatives:** design option 1 (left, Figure 19) was the preferred option. Participants also liked option 3 (right, Figure 19), but not so much option 2 with the lighter colours (center, Figure 19).

FIGURE 19 - THE THREE ALTERNATIVE VERSIONS OF THE HOMEPAGE SUBMITTED TO THE PARTICIPANTS. FROM LEFT TO RIGHT: OPTION 1, OPTION 2, OPTION 3.

- "Join GoTriple" section:** it was commented that the "Join GoTriple" section (Figure 20) looked to be promoting the mobile app version of the platform due to the inclusion of the mobile phone.

FIGURE 20 - JOIN GOTRIPLE MOCKUP OF THE HOMEPAGE.

4.5.4 How to improve the GoTriple design

It seems from the feedback given that the participants generally liked the look and feel of the search features, but they gave some useful suggestions for how it could be improved. At a high level these suggestions included:

- The clear labelling of the new innovative services, such as "Annotation", "Knowledge Map" and "Visual" overview.
- Terms such as "Pundit" would need more explanation as to what it is - ie. Annotation service.
- Hover-over explanations of what these are may be required (or access to a short help video to introduce them to users).
- Ensure the language options are explained: it is a new concept that people are as yet unfamiliar with and therefore not certain how it works.
- Possible slight adjustments to the layout to reflect some of the comments made above. In particular, having a clearly visible "Search" term when results are displayed.
- Improved contrast in colour displays for the "visual" information provided.

5 | FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The five workshops held in Task 3.4 around dashboards and profile pages allowed us to look at the design of these sections from the perspective of real users. This is a fundamental approach to the design of any service or product and all the takeaways listed in section "4 Insights" are the tangible proof of how effective the workshops were.

Concerning the methodology, the project team members had to learn how to conduct co-design workshops remotely due to the pandemic, adapting the methodologies they knew (like Post up, voting and Crazy 8's) to the remote virtual environment. Despite initial concerns, holding the workshops remotely has worked well and delivered great results, also thanks to the tools used (Miro and Zoom). The only methodology that proved more problematic to run remotely was the Crazy 8's, for which an in-person solution would have been probably more effective.

In some cases, the results of the workshops confirmed the project team's early assumptions (like that GoTriple should be used for discovery but also for finding and connecting with peers). And in many cases, the workshops introduced new solutions that we hadn't thought of (like the importance of keywords as a sublevel for Disciplines).

All the outcomes of the workshops are now in the hands of the designers of the user experience and of the interface. They will have to select the ideas that are feasible and relevant for the scope of the project and then integrate them into the design of the GoTriple's interface.

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